

Direct electrochemical synthesis of coordination compounds of copper(II) halides : Part I

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Abstract : The coordination compounds of Cu^{II} halides were synthesized by electrolyzing the aqueous solution (1 : 1 mixture of conductivity water and rectified spirit) of halogen (chlorine, bromine or iodine) and ligand (1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl or pyridine) at sacrificial copper anode and inert platinum cathode. All these products have been characterized by elemental analysis, infrared spectral data and other physical methods. Current efficiencies of all these systems are quite high.

Keywords : Electrochemical synthesis, copper(II) halides, coordination compounds.

Introduction

Electrochemical technique has been used as a tool for the synthesis of a variety of organic¹⁻⁴, inorganic⁵⁻⁸ compounds and nano-particles^{9,10}. A close study of technique reveals that the technique provides single step, direct route to carry out synthesis with high product yield. In continuation to our interest in synthetic inorganic chemistry¹¹⁻¹⁵. We report in the present communication the electrochemical synthesis of the coordination compounds of copper(II) halides.

Results and discussion

In the present studies the emphasis is on the use of electrochemical technique as a synthetic tool for the synthesis of coordination compounds of copper(II) halides and isolation of the pure product in a shorter time is the ultimate goal of the study. Therefore, all these electrolytic reactions have been conducted at high potential, the electrolysis of solution of halogen (chlorine, bromine or iodine) alongwith ligand (1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl or pyridine), have been carried out at sacrificial copper anode and inert platinum cathode in H-type pyrex glass cell. The products obtained from anode compartment are soluble in commonly used organic solvents like acetonitrile, acetone, dimethylsulphoxide and *N,N*-dimethyl formamide. Melting point determination of these prod-

ucts shows that these products do not melt up to 300 °C, but decompose in temperature range of 150-250 °C. The decomposition of these products is indicated from the change in colour of the compound in this temperature range. Elemental analysis of these products corresponds to 1 : 2 : 1 stoichiometry and that of pyridine correspond to 1 : 2 : 2 stoichiometry of copper, halogen and ligand. Molecular weight of two of these products have also been determined which are in line with the elemental data. Both elemental analysis data and molecular weight data conform to molecular formula, CuX₂L_n (in case of electrolysis of chlorine and bromine) and CuI₂L_n.6.5H₂O.

Infrared spectral data of all these products have been recorded in the region of 4000-450 cm⁻¹. The characteristic bands appear in the regions of 1625-1225 cm⁻¹ and 855-720 cm⁻¹.

Survey of literature¹⁶ reveals that $\nu(\text{Cu-Cl})$, $\nu(\text{Cu-Br})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-I})$ bands appear in the region of 220-100 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ band appears around 300 cm⁻¹. The bands due to $\nu(\text{C=C})$, $\nu(\text{C=N})$ and $\delta(\text{C-H})$ ring deformation of 1,10-phenanthroline¹⁷ are present in the region of 1620-1217 cm⁻¹ and 849-733 cm⁻¹. The bands appearing in the region of 1625-1225 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C=C})$ and $\nu(\text{C=N})$ stretching modes and the bands present in the region of 855-721 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to $\delta(\text{C-H})$ and ring deformation modes of 1,10-

phenanthroline. Presence of these bands at shifted position indicates the coordination of the ligand to metal.

The infrared spectral data of the products of pyridine and 2,2'-bipyridyl show characteristic bands in the region of 3053-3026, 1597-1037 and 769-729 cm^{-1} . Literature reveals¹⁷⁻²⁰ that characteristic bands due to 2,2'-bipyridyl and pyridine appear in the region of 3050-3020, 1603-1029 and 755-740 cm^{-1} . The bands present in the region of 1597-1037 cm^{-1} may be attributed to stretching modes of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and bands present in the region of 3053-3026 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ stretching mode, while the bands present in the region of 769-729 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ and ring deformation modes of 2,2'-bipyridyl and pyridine. The presence of these bands at shifted positions indicates the coordination of ligand to metal. In the products the $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{X})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$ bands have not been observed due to limitation of instrument. Efforts have been done to carry out X-ray crystallography but the crystals obtained do not diffract.

Current efficiencies of these systems have also been determined and are listed in Table 1. The data reveal that current efficiencies of all these systems are quite high.

High current efficiencies of these systems indicate that the reactions leading to the formation of coordination compounds of copper(II) halides are the predominant reactions of these systems. The reaction scheme may be written as :

At inert cathode :

At sacrificial anode :

where $n = 1$, when L is 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl and $n = 2$, when L is pyridine.

The electrochemical synthetic technique thus provides a direct route for the synthesis of coordination compounds of copper(II) halides which are otherwise difficult to prepare through traditional synthetic methods. In addition, the present method is single pot, single step and can be conducted at room temperature by using routine laboratory chemicals, apparatus and metal as reagent.

Experimental

Reagents and solvent : Water was refluxed by adding potassium permanganate and a pellet of potassium hy-

Table 1. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical data, current efficiencies and other related data of electrolytic products of halogen + ligand systems at copper anode

Potential : 30 V, current in coulombs : 162

System	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :				Current efficiency (gram equivalent/Faraday)
			Found (Calcd.)				
			Cu	C	H	N	
Chlorine + 1,10-phenanthroline	$\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)$	Green	19.6 (20.1)	44.9 (45.8)	2.5 (2.5)	8.5 (8.8)	0.93
Chlorine + 2,2'-bipyridyl	$\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)$	Blue	20.3 (21.8)	41.3 (41.3)	2.7 (2.7)	9.5 (9.6)	0.95
Bromine + 1,10-phenanthroline	$\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)$	Green	15.2 (15.7)	40.4 (35.7)	2.2 (1.9)	7.0 (6.9)	0.86
Bromine + 2,2'-bipyridyl	$\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)$	Blue	16.5 (16.7)	34.6 (31.6)	2.0 (2.1)	7.8 (7.3)	0.72
Bromine + pyridine	$\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_2$	Light green	16.5 (16.6)	- (31.4)	- (2.6)	- (7.3)	0.92
Iodine + 1,10-phenanthroline	$\text{CuI}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2) \cdot 6.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	9.9 (10.3)	23.8 (23.4)	2.9 (3.4)	5.0 (4.5)	0.92
Iodine + 2,2'-bipyridyl	$\text{CuI}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2) \cdot 6.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	9.6 (10.7)	20.0 (20.3)	3.1 (3.5)	4.2 (4.7)	0.95
Iodine + pyridine	$\text{CuI}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2 \cdot 6.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dirty white	9.7 (10.7)	17.8 (20.2)	2.3 (3.8)	4.0 (4.7)	0.86

dioxide and then was fractionally distilled. Rectified spirit was fractionally distilled. Mixture (1 : 1) of conductivity water and rectified spirit was used as solvent in all these reactions. Chlorine gas was prepared by adding concentrated hydrochloric acid onto small amount of potassium permanganate crystals in a flask and was directly passed into the reaction mixture. Other organic compounds were used as procured.

Procedure and technique :

Electrolysis of solution of halogen (chlorine, bromine or iodine), 0.5 g of ligand (1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl or pyridine) has been conducted at copper anode and platinum cathode in a H-type pyrex glass cell. Potassium halide (respective) was used as supporting electrolyte in all these reactions. The potential across the electrodes was adjusted so that a current of 1.5 mA passed through the solution. The electrolytic solution was stirred efficiently using magnetic stirrer (Remi make). The electrolytic cell can be represented as :

where $\text{Cu}_{(+)}$ and $\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ represents copper anode and platinum cathode.

X_2 represents chlorine, bromine or iodine and L represents 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl or pyridine. KX represents potassium chloride, potassium bromide or potassium iodide.

In case of iodine systems, the solid product separated in the anode compartment after three hours of electrolysis, which was washed with conductivity water and finally with rectified spirit and then dried. However, in chlorine or bromine no product was separated, therefore after electrolysis of three hours, reaction mixture from anode compartment was distilled. The concentrated solution was transferred to a beaker containing a chip and was kept for one day. The coloured crystals were separated out.

Copper contents in the products were determined volumetrically²¹. Microanalysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents in these products have also been car-

ried out. Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI) in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} using potassium bromide pellets. Molecular weights were determined by using Finnagin Mat LCQ mass spectrometer.

The current efficiencies (gram equivalents of metal dissolved per Faraday of electricity passed) of all these reactions were determined by electrolysing the above systems for exactly one hour at a constant current of 15 mA.

References

1. Tae-Hun Kim and Su Moon Park, *Electrochimica Acta*, 2005, **50**, 1461.
2. H. A. Rehan, *Polymer International*, 2003, **52**, 218.
3. Youichi Tsuchiya and Hisashi Fujihara, *Electrochemistry*, 2002, **70**, 584.
4. Jay D. Wadhawan, Frank Marken, Richard G. Compton, Steve D. Bull and Stephen G. Devis, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 87.
5. Harpreet Kaur, J. S. Banait and Baljit Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2010, **3**, 1073.
6. A. Sousa Padraes, J. Romero, J. A. Garcia-Vazquez, M. L. Duran, I. Casanova and A. Sousa, *Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 1379.
7. Jesus Castro, Santiago Cabaleiro, P. P. Lourido, J. Romero and Jose A. Garcia-Vazquaz, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 2002, **628**, 1210.
8. M. A. Rauchfuss and S. R. T. B. Wilson, *Organomet.*, 2005, **22**, 1619.
9. J. I. A. Wei, X. U. Mao-Wen, B. A. D. Shu-Juan and J. I. A. Dian-Zeng, *J. Inorg. Mat.*, 2010, **25**, 1335.
10. Dinesh Pratap Singh and Onkar Nath Srivastava, *J. Nanosci. Nanotech.*, 2009, **9**, 5515.
11. J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Harpreet Kaur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1.
12. J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Harpreet Kaur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 261.
13. Harpreet Kaur, J. S. Banait and Baljit Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2010, **3**, 1073.
14. J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Harpreet Kaur, *Port. Electrochim. Acta*, 2007, **25**, 435.
15. J. S. Banait and Baljit Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 641.
16. A. Graham Bowmaker, E. Sue Boyd, V. John Hanna, D. Robert Hart, C. Peter Healy, W. Brain Skelton and H. Allan White, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2722.
17. M. M. Campos-Valette, R. E. Clavijo, F.

- Mendizabal, W. Zamudio, Ruth Baraona and G. Diaz, *Vib. Spect.*, 1996, **12**, 37.
18. Lucilea Rnaudetr, Olandb Ougon, Buu Ban, Pierrette Charpin, Jacques Isabey, Monique Lance, Martine Nierlich and Julien Vigner, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1990, **68**, 507.
19. Ziya Kantarci, *Commun. Fac. Sci. Univ. Ank. Series A₂, A₃*, 1988, **37**, 53.
20. S. Akyuz, A. B. Dempster and R. L. Morehouse, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1973, **17**, 1075.
21. Vogel's, "Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", Longman Group, UK, 1989.